

An Analytical Observational Study to Assess the Role of Serum CA125 Levels in Predicting the Outcome of Threatened Abortion

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to evaluate the role of serum CA-125 in predicting potential pregnancy outcome of bleeding in early pregnancy (threatened abortion).

Methods: This analytical observational study was conducted after clearance from the Institutional Ethical committee, in the Department of Pathology, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur Bihar, India during the period of one year. 100 patients met inclusion criteria and included in the study.

Results: We found statistically significant increase of CA125 in aborted patients when compared to patients that continued their pregnancy after 20 weeks (48.36±36.94 and 116.28±81.04 respectively). Maximum number of patients was in primigravida. Out of the 50 patients in case, 45 (90%) were primigravida and 5 (10%) were multigravida. There was no statistical difference in distribution of patients based on parity and gestational weeks. 70% of patients of threatened abortion with maternal serum CA 125 level of more than 60 IU/ml in case while 28% of patients of threatened abortion with maternal serum CA125 level in control of more than 60 IU/ml continued to the period of viability. Statistically the difference was significant with p value of <0.001.

Conclusion: Maternal serum CA-125 is concluded to be a hopeful biomarker to predict potential pregnancy outcome in threatened abortion.

Keywords: Threatened, abortion, CA-125, biomarker

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Introduction:

Abortion is defined as the loss of pregnancy before the age of fetal viability, that is, at a stage when the embryo or fetus is not capable of surviving independently. WHO defines abortion as termination of pregnancy before 20 weeks of gestation or delivery of a fetus weighing less than < 500 g. Threatened abortion is defined as bleeding per vaginum during first half of pregnancy, without cervical dilatation and intact fetal cardiac activity on USG. It is

reported to occur in approximately 1/5th of pregnancies, results in miscarriage in 3-16% of cases and causes significant emotional distress & financial burden to the woman and her family. In view of uncertainty in predicting the potential outcome of threatened abortion, it is challenging to the healthcare provider also. [1-3]

CA-125 is a member of the mucin family glycoproteins, present in tissue derived

from embryonic coelom. Genital or non-genital sources may account for a raised CA-125 level. Human amniotic fluid shows high levels of CA-125 with amnion being its major source. Its levels are increased in early pregnancy and immediately after birth, thus implicating the disintegration of the maternal decidua and amnion. This infers that any disruption of the decidua or fetal membranes' basement membrane would cause a surge in maternal CA-125 and predict a subsequent miscarriage. [4-6] Various studies have been done to use ultrasonographic and biochemical markers to predict the outcome of threatened abortion, however results have not been satisfactory. CA-125, serum beta- hCG, progesterone, HPL, AFP are commonly studied biochemical markers.

CA-125 can be used as a predictive marker for subsequent outcome of pregnancy. CA-125 (cancer antigen 125, carcinoma antigen 125, or carbohydrate antigen 125) is cell surface high molecular weight glycoprotein present in tissue derived from embryonic coelomic. It has been found in high concentration in human amniotic fluid with amnion being major source of it. During pregnancy, disruption of the epithelial basement membrane of the fetal membrane or disruption of the decidua could theoretically lead to rise in maternal CA 125 level, thus can be used as a predictor of subsequent spontaneous abortion. Its levels are increased in early pregnancy and immediately after birth [5], thus implicating the disintegration of the maternal decidua (i.e., blastocyst implantation and placental separation) as a possible source of the tumor marker elevation. [6]

Therefore, the elevated serum CA 125 levels in women with threatened abortion implicate poor outcome in future. This test is rather sensitive in determining the progression to the pregnancy loss.

Materials and Methods

This analytical observational study was conducted after clearance from the Institutional Ethical committee, in the Department of Pathology, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur Bihar, India during the period of one year. 100 patients met inclusion criteria and included in the study.

Inclusion criteria

- All the women of age group from 20-40 yrs. presenting to Obstetrics OPD
- Gestational age ranging from 7-14 weeks
- Singleton spontaneous pregnancy
- Presenting with complain of vaginal bleeding or spotting.
- A viable gestational sac or living embryo, verified by the cardiac activity
- Antenatal females without any obvious sign of abortion as control group

Exclusion criteria

- Patients with history of general medical disease e.g. Diabetes or thyroid disease
- Patients with presence of local (gynecological) disease e.g. Fibroid or adnexal mass
- Patients with history of RPL
- Uterine anomalies
- Other causes of raised serum CA125 level such as chronic pelvis infections, ovarian cyst and endometriosis

Methodology

The cases were recruited from obstetrics OPD of SKMCH, Muzaffarpur Bihar, India with complaint of bleeding per vaginum, at gestation age between 7 to 14 weeks and fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The purpose of the study was explained to the participants and an informed written consent was taken. The approval from the Ethics committee of the institution was taken.

Detailed history was taken from all the study participants. Complete general physical examination, systemic and obstetric examination was done. All

routine antenatal blood investigations and serum CA 125 levels were done. Gestational age, fetal viability, and intrauterine singleton pregnancy was confirmed by Ultrasonography. All participants were followed till term. The patients were divided into cases and control. The cases were further divided as Group A, in whom the pregnancy continued and Group B, who aborted.

Statistical analysis

The data was entered into the Microsoft excel and the statistical analysis was

performed by statistical software SPSS version 25.0. The Quantitative (Numerical variables) were present in the form of mean and SD and the Qualitative (Categorical variables) were present in the form of frequency and percentage. The student t-test was used for comparing the mean values between the 2 groups whereas chi-square/ fishers exact test was applied for comparing the frequency. The p-value was considered to be significant when less than 0.05.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of study population

		Case	Control	P value
Age (years)		24.23±3.53	24.33±3.06	0.620
GA (weeks)		9.7±1.52	9.28±1.30	0.230
Gravidity	1	28 (56)	22 (44)	0.660
	2	14 (28)	16 (32)	
	>3	8 (16)	12 (24)	
Parity	Primipara	45 (90)	46 (92)	0.160
	Multipara	5 (10)	4 (8)	
Hormonal levels	CA.125(IU/ml)	48.36±36.94	116.28±81.04	< 0.0001

We found statistically significant increase of CA125 in aborted patients when compared to patients that continued their pregnancy after 20 weeks (48.36±36.94 and 116.28±81.04 respectively). Maximum number of patients was in

primigravida. Out of the 50 patients in case, 45 (90%) were primigravida and 5 (10%) were multigravida. There was no statistical difference in distribution of patients based on parity and gestational weeks.

Table 2: Distribution of study population according to maternal CA 125 levels

CA 125 (in IU / ml)	Result		Total
	Case	Control	
> 60	35 (70)	14 (28)	49
<60	15 (30)	36 (72)	51
Total	50	50	100

70% of patients of threatened abortion with maternal serum CA 125 level of more than 60 IU/ml in case while 28% of patients of threatened abortion with maternal serum CA125 level in control of more than 60 IU/ml continued to the period of viability.

Table 3: Distribution based on serum CA125 values

Groups	CA125			t-test value	p-value
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference		
Case	58.04	12.56	38.68	18.134	0.001
Control	19.37	5.70			

Statistically the difference was significant with p value of <0.001.

Discussion

First-trimester bleeding is one of the most common obstetric complications, occurring in 25% of all pregnancies. [7] More than 80 percent of abortions occur in the first 12 weeks of pregnancy and at least half result from chromosomal anomalies. After the first trimester, both the abortion rate and the incidence of chromosomal anomalies decrease. [8] The clinical diagnosis of threatened miscarriage is presumed when bloody vaginal discharge or bleeding appears through a closed cervical os during the first half of pregnancy. [9] Ultrasonography, serial serum quantitative assessment of B-subunit of human chorionic gonadotropins (B-hCG), serum cancer antigen -125 (CA-125) and serum progesterone values measured alone or in various combinations, have proven helpful in ascertaining if a live intrauterine pregnancy is present. [8]

In the present work, we found statistically significant increase of CA125 in aborted patients when compared to patients that continued their pregnancy after 20 weeks (48.36 ± 36.94 and 116.28 ± 81.04 respectively). In addition, the sensitivity of CA125 in prediction of abortion in studied females was 83.33% and specificity was 92.62% at a cutoff value of > 60 IU/ml. Our study can be compared with the work of Abd-Elrau of M Oun et al (2018). [10] Their study included 110 women with manifestations of first trimester threatened miscarriage. CA 125 levels ranged from 8 to 77 IU/ml, and there was statistically significant decrease of CA125 in group (A) (continued) when compared to group (B) (aborted) (19.45 ± 5.57 vs 53.83 ± 9.48 respectively). Gidwani et al (2019) [2] studied 60 patients of threatened abortion and followed them upto 20 weeks. They took 60 IU/ml as cut off limit. In their study it was noted that with maternal serum CA 125 level of more than 60 IU/ml, 72.2% patients aborted while 27.8% of patients continued their

pregnancy; while with serum CA 125 level lesser than 60 IU/ml, 11.9% of patients aborted whereas 88.1% of patients continued their pregnancy. The difference was statistically significant with p value of < 0.001 .

Concluding CA125 is as a good screening tool in patients with threatened miscarriage to predict pregnancies who developed to complete abortion. It had the advantage of being available and cheap test that can be used in screening and follow up of management in patients with threatened abortion. In agreement with the results of the present work, (Al Mohamady et al. (2016) [11] reported that, the level of serum CA-125 for the threatened miscarriage (miscarried) group was 54.28 ± 11.4 IU/ml; while for the threatened miscarriage (continued) group it was 18.81 ± 8.02 IU/ml. The difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.001$). They added, using a ROC curve for CA-125 in predicting the outcome of pregnancy in threatened miscarriage cases, the cut-off limit of 31.2 IU/ml of CA-125 level achieved sensitivity of 96.2% and specificity of 100%. CA-125 level above 31.2 IU/ml predicted occurrence of miscarriage with an overall accuracy of 99.4%.

Abd Elrau of M Ounet. al. (2018) [10] studied 110 females and divided them in two groups, Group A with continued pregnancy and Group B with miscarriage. These two groups were compared as regards ultrasonography and serum CA 125. The levels of CA125 were significantly low in patients who continued their pregnancy in comparison to patients who aborted (19.45 ± 5.57 vs 53.83 ± 9.48). Results of Marwa Eid et al (2017) [12] also showed that women who continued their first trimester of pregnancy showed a significantly lower level of CA 125 when compared with those who aborted. Sudha, Krishna Sinha (2020) studied 100 patients with threatened abortion. At 20 weeks POG, 32% patients aborted while in 68%,

pregnancy continued. According to their study mean maternal serum CA 125 level was 117.06 IU/ml in patients who aborted and 49.11 IU/ml in patients who continued their pregnancy till term (P value < 0.0001). [13]

Several cut-off values were suggested in other studies in order to predict pregnancy outcome in early viable pregnancies complicated by vaginal bleeding. In this study, a cut-off limit of 60 IU/ml of CA-125 level was suggested, with a sensitivity of 83.33% and specificity of 92.62%. Fiegler et al. (2003) [14] used a cut-off value of 66.5 IU/ml with a sensitivity of 55%. Azougi et al. (1996) used a 125 IU/ml as a cut-off value and reported a 100% sensitivity and specificity. [15] We have examined the potential value of serum CA 125 in predicting the future of a pregnancy in question. A proper prediction of how the pregnancy ends in a patient with symptoms of an abortive miscarriage allows shortening the time of hospitalisation, reducing the symptomatic and emotional problems resulting from waiting for the result of treatment. [16]

Conclusion

Bleeding in early pregnancy can be a bewildering experience for any pregnant women, up to 50% of such pregnancies are usually lost. CA125 is a non-invasive and a quick method that can be used to prognosticate the outcome of pregnancies with threatened abortion. Our study revealed that the serum CA-125 level estimation is a useful in women with threatened abortion and pregnancy loss as it is cost effective, with high sensitivity and specificity and thus should be recommended with other routine antenatal investigations.

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